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(11)

**TUTELARY DEITIES OF SOUTH ODISHA:
RITUAL PRACTICES AND ROYAL PATRONAGE
(Circa. 16th- 19th century CE)**

The former rulers of Odisha played an important role in the growth and development of the worship of gods and goddesses. To establish and strengthen their power as local rulers, they depended on the assistance and protection of the main local goddess, who was in most cases a tribal deity. Due to a strong belief in her power, she received the status of a royal family's tutelary deity; as such, she was also considered a protective goddess of the territory. Since the rulers promoted her cult and worship, she often acquired supra-regional recognition. These tutelary deities of the former royal families of Odisha form a specific group of deities, many of whom have their roots in the tribal fold.² They exert a strong integrative influence in these particular regions. A network of relationships may also result from a family splitting up, as was the case within the Khemundi Raj family. The royal families of Parlakhemundi, Badakhemundi and Sanakhemundi join in worshipping the goddess Manikeswari. The most prominent goddess Manikeswari, is worshipped widely in Kalahandi, Rayagada and Ganjam districts, and the goddess Sambaleswari, is known in the Sambalpur, Bolangir and Sundargarh areas. Similarly, Bhattarika of Baramba, Maninageswari of Ranpur, and Carcika of Banki are some instances of deities who ascended from the status of tribal deities to that of Istadevatas.

This paper focuses on the tutelary deities of south Odisha most importantly Khambheswari, Mohuri Kalua, Thakurani, Majhighariani and Markama, their ritual activities and patronisation by little kings of Odisha. One of the most prominent characteristics of the religious life of south Odisha is the greater significance accorded to those deities of the little tradition who are regarded as mother goddesses or earth goddesses.

Khambheswari in Aska:

The goddess *Khambheshvari* from Aska, a vibrant trading town in Ganjam, in the valley of the river Rushikulya, belongs to a group of goddesses known as Stambheshvari which means 'goddess of the pillar', alluding to the fact that the images of this goddess consist overwhelmingly of wooden posts. In Aska itself, we find an interesting doubling up of the material representation of the goddess in front of the sacrificial site stands the non-iconic symbol of a wooden post, while in the sanctum opposite is a stone idol. This stone image of Khambheshvari, the focus of the pujas, consists of a body in the form of a

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² B. Schnepel, 1993. 'Die Schutzgöttinnen: Tribale Gottheiten in Sudorissa (Indien) und ihre Patronage durch hinduistische Kleinkönige', *Anthropos* 88, 337-50.

lingam, roughly 1.20 metres high and with a diameter of about 40 centimetres. Attached to this stone is a round, vermilion-coloured head made out of a sheet of cardboard on which three golden eyes and a mouth with a protruding tongue have been glued. For the puja, Khambheshvari is dressed in splendid silk robes and hung with garlands of flowers. I was allowed to photograph the goddess, for which the priest dressed her up especially. However, the head of the temple, who arrived later, was incensed that on this occasion Khambheshvari had not been adorned with a cardboard construction of eight arms (which was kept in the storeroom of the temple). A further stage in her anthropomorphization would therefore have been possible, though it finds expression only on special occasions.¹

The priests at the temple of Khambheshvari belong to the low-ranking caste of 'gardeners' (*mallis*). The puja is performed twice daily, in the early morning and the evening, and consists of the offering of lamps, incense, flowers, food and the sounding of a bell hung in front of the entrance. Among the gifts presented are coconuts, bananas, leaves in the shape of a trident called *belo-patra*, and the red flowers of the *mandara* tree. Only rarely do animal sacrifices take place in the temple of Khambheshvari, though they are carried out on the occasion of the Durga puja in autumn and the *caitra parva* (an originally tribal festival based on the symbolism of the hunt) in spring. It should also be mentioned that a small movable figure of brass is carried around the temple or the town in a procession during these festivals and on Sankranti days. This is Khambheshvari's mobile substitute (*calanti pratima*), which otherwise stands next to her in the temple.

One legend about Khambheshvari, according to a priest in the temple at Aska, illustrates the original relationship of the goddess with the forest region and its inhabitants. It is said that Khambheshvari appeared in a dream to a man living in the forest called Khambhamuni and demanded from him that he worship her as a goddess. The beautiful goddess lived with the old man for a time as if she were his daughter, though this was regarded with suspicion by passers-by. To avoid getting a bad name, Khambhamuni revealed the true nature of the goddess, who immediately disappeared. Subsequently, Khambheshvari played practical jokes on the old man, for example, by buying bangles and having him pay for them. Once she appeared suddenly before him with a baby torn to pieces on her arm. Eventually, the old man lost his patience and slapped her, upon which Khambheshvari made it known that the time of her childish play (*balyalila*) was over, that Khambhamuni must die, and that from that day on she was to be worshipped at that very same spot by his son.²

Mahuri Kalua and Budhi Thakurani in Berhampur:

The temple of another goddess called *Mohuri Kalua* is situated some twelve kilometres west of Berhampur, near the Kerandi Hills. Directly behind the temple is a steeply rising hill, with a stony path leading up to its summit. After an arduous ascent, one passes through a narrow cleft to a shelter beneath three large rocks which stand

¹ . _____, 2002. "Tutelaty deities: The Royal Patronage of Tribal Goddesses" in *The Jungle King*, pp. 233.

² . A.K. Rath, 1987. *Studies on Some Aspects of the History and Culture of Orissa*, Calcutta: Punthi Pustak. Pp. 80-89.

together like a house of cards. In this cave is the original goddess in the form of a small, conically shaped heap of earth about fifty centimetres high. A vermilion head of cardboard decorated with golden eyes and a protruding tongue is placed on top of this earthen body and a tiara of peacock feathers is fixed above the figure. Puja is offered to the goddess on the hill twice a week, on Sundays and Tuesdays. However, animal sacrifices are not made here because, according to the priest, it is too difficult to get animals up there. It is said that to spare her devotees the tiresome climb, Mohuri Kalua threw a vessel from the hill and at the point at which it landed the main temple now stands.

The temple at the foot of the hill is of a medium size and rectangular in shape. At the back are some houses in which live the priests, who come from *bhandari or barbar* caste. To one side a small temple dedicated to Siva. The walls of the entrance hall of the main temple are decorated with motifs of the goddess Kali. The image of goddess Mahuri Kalua consists of a conical body, roughly 1.20 meters in height. Puja is offered three times a day. When pilgrims step in front of the goddess with their gifts, a priest sitting in front of Mohuri Kalua offers candlelight, incense, flowers, leaves, coconut milk, bananas and other items in a shortened form of the puja ceremony. While this is going on, the supplicant stands reverently praying in front of the balustrade or rings one of the many bells that hang from the roof. Some, to show their great devotion, prostrate themselves on the ground, with their faces to the floor and folded hands outstretched towards the goddess, praying and occasionally hitting their foreheads on the floor. The goddess is offered animal sacrifices twice a week, mainly goats and chickens, which are killed in a rather remote grove outside the temple complex. A foreleg of the goat is offered to the goddess. Twice a week, the snake that lives in the body of the goddess (in the termite mound, that is) is worshipped by the priests behind closed doors and fed with milk. The greatest festival of the year takes place on sankranti day which marks the entrance of the sun into the zodiac called mesa. On this festival, besides thousands of pilgrims, the Mohuri raja personally visits the goddess. Many goats are killed and it is said that earlier Mohuri kings offered human sacrifices on this occasion.

Together with Mohuri Kalua, a look should be taken at the goddess *Budhi Thakurani*, the patron deity of the large trading city of Berhampur, since this goddess is regarded by many of the inhabitants of the area as another manifestation of Mohuri Kalua. *Budhi Thakurani* is one of the most important goddesses of the coastal region of southern Odisha. Tens of thousands of people take part in her festival, the *Thakurani yatra*, which takes place every two or three years and lasts for several weeks. The celebration of this festival in spring (in the month of *Chaitra*) acquires special significance in the eyes of many, if there has been a long period without a good harvest or the country has been plagued by epidemics. The *Thakurani yatra* offers an occasion for ritual costume, pantomimes and lively, occasionally ecstatic dancing. The celebrations sometimes have the character of a ritual of reversal or a ritual of violence. These excesses are the main reason why the collector gives his approval for the holding of the festival reluctantly.

Budhi Thakurani is represented by a stone roughly forty centimetres high, on to which is placed a red cardboard mask representing a face. During the *Thakurani*

yatra, she is also worshipped in the form of a lotus blossom. Many elements of the daily cult in the Thakurani temple are similar to those found in the temple of Mohuri Kalua. However, in Berhampur sacrifices are frequently made—up to several times a day. The sacrificial site is in the temple complex itself, behind a wall at the foot of a neem or margosa tree, which is regarded as sacred. The severed heads of the sacrificial victims, mostly goats and chickens, but in earlier times also occasionally humans, are offered to the goddess. The priests belong to the weaver or dera caste, usually in India a low, often even derided caste,¹ though in Berhampur they are influential merchants of Telugu descent. The head of a leading family of this caste called desi *behera*, is regarded as the ‘father’ of the goddess, a fact which also finds ritual expression in the Thakurani yatra and which alludes to the fact that, in the case of Budhi Thakurani, we have less a ‘mother’ goddess than a ‘daughter’ goddess.

Majhighraiani in Rayagada:

Maa Majhighraiani, a further example of a tribal goddess subjected to the process of Hinduization is from the hill area of Koraput District. It will be recalled that under Viswanatha Deo (1521-1571 CE), the fourth ruler of the Suryavamsha dynasty, the royal capital was moved for a time from Nandapur to Rayagada. One of the most important temples in present-day Rayagada, which is dedicated to the goddess Majhighraiani, dates from the time of Viswanatha, when it probably already possessed central ritual importance for the inhabitants of the area. If one makes one’s way from the centre of Rayagada to this temple today, one first comes to a quarter of the town which can be identified as the old fortress area through the remains of a wall. A few hundred meters before the temple is a large banyan tree with many small white stones lying under it. A split coconut, some scattered flowers, several belo patra leaves, and red and white spots painted on the large monolithic block of stone in front of the tree indicate that this is a sacred site. According to local information, the stones lying scattered beneath the tree were gifts made to the goddess by adivasis who had come to the town.²

After crossing a railway line built in the, there is a well-kept temple dedicated to Majhighraiani. Today, this temple is one of the most popular as well as the richest in south Odisha, with several thousand visitors daily, especially on Sunday. The flow of pilgrims is controlled using a ticketing and barrier system. However, the temple acquired its present size and splendour only some decades ago. It is reported that while constructing the railway line, a bridge being built not far from the temple collapsed on several occasions. According to local tradition, Majhighraiani did this to have a bigger temple built for her by the railway company. It is not known precisely when the new temple was constructed, but an eyewitness describes the temple as being in ruins in 1930. Old photographs also testify to the immediate environs of the temple, which today are well-groomed, being overgrown and covered with many trees and bushes.

¹. Jordan-Horstmann, M. 1972. “Der dumme Weber: Spotterzahlungen beiden Mundas” , in *Anthropos* 67, Pp. 564-85.

². B. Schnepel, 2002. *Tutelary deities: The Royal Patronage of Tribal Goddesses in The Jungle King*, pp. 238.

Even the site of the legendary ritual death by burning (*sati*) of the 116 consorts of Viswanatha, located next to the temple, looks neglected in the old photographs. Today this is a small, fenced-off park, in which the deified wives are ritually honoured on sankranti days.¹

The figure of Majhighariani consists of seven white stones, the largest of which forms a head coloured in vermilion. The face is characterized by expressive eyes, black eyebrows, a silver nose, a golden mouth and a protruding silver tongue. The head is wreathed in a gold ornament in the shape of a crown and the image is garlanded with red and white flowers hung around the head. The seven stones can hardly be made out under this, 'mask'. Only when the sacred inner space is cleaned a task that is undertaken after visiting time are the naked stones revealed.

The greatest festivals of the year at the Majhighariani temple are Durgapuja in autumn and *caitra* parva in spring. Until 1890, human sacrifice is said to have taken place on the eighth night of the Durga *puja*. This was carried out at a stone especially set aside for it, called the 'priest's stone' (*jani pathara*), probably the stone with red and white spots under the tree in front of the temple.² Today, humans are replaced by a particular type of sheep. As this animal can be found only in remote areas, its sacrifice can be allocated to the realm of tribal culture. After the sacrifice, the blood is collected and brought to the goddess, while the body and head go to members of the sweeper caste. Even on a normal day, a large number of goats and chickens are sacrificed. In addition, coconuts, bananas, rice and other vegetable gifts are offered, if the request is a minor one or the pilgrim's financial means are not enough to permit a blood sacrifice. The priests of the Majhighariani temple come from the caste of the foot soldiers or *paiks*.

Markama in Bissamcuttack:

Markama is the tutelary goddess of Bissamcuttack town and one of the most powerful goddesses of the estate, she is ascribed great effectiveness by her devotees, especially when it comes to holding witchcraft, demons or evil spirits at bay. *Markama's* temple lies in a grove somewhat outside the town. The image of the goddess consists of a large black stone with a smaller stone on top. The latter forms a red-coloured head, covered all over with silver eyes and a protruding tongue. The larger stone, which functions as the body, is usually decorated with red garments. During *puja* the head of the goddess is decorated with garlands of red and white flowers (made up like a splendid head of hair). During the services, burning candles, coconuts and many flowers with red, blue and yellow blossoms are placed on the ground in front of the deity; during sacrifices, *Markama* is also decorated with many green *belo patra* leaves. Right next to her stands a sword with red and white stripes, which acts as her substitute in processions. This 'stage' is surrounded by a stone structure, before whose semi-circular opening the priests perform their services. If one takes a few steps back and looks at the whole scenario, one receives the impression of looking into the open muzzle of a lion.

In order to reach *Markama's* dwelling in her medium-sized temple, raised

¹ . K.B. Singh Deo, 1939. *Nandapur: A Forsaken Kingdom*, Cuttack: Utkal Sahitya Press. Pp. 14-17

² . W. Francis, 1907. *Madras District Gazetteers: Vizagapatnam*, Madras: Government Press. Pp. 302.

somewhat on a mound of earth, one must climb ten stone steps. At the foot of this ascent are five wooden posts about a meter high, on which slight notches hint at heads and waists. Sacrificial animals which have been dedicated to the goddess are tied to these posts before being killed directly in the sight of the goddess. In the middle of the sandy square in front of the temple lies a flat stone painted with twenty red spots surrounded with white to represent the human sacrifices that were carried out at one time. The heads and a few blood of the sacrificial animals are offered to the goddess and to the priest sitting in front of the image, who is possessed by her on these occasions. During the daily puja, the gifts consist of coconuts, bananas, millet, the juice of a particular tree, *Mandara* blossoms, sweets, red cloth and other items. The greatest festivals of the year are the two Durga *pujas* in autumn and spring. As in the case of Majhighariani, the priests of the Markama temple belong to the warrior caste of paiks.¹

While the theme of this legend is the connection of the goddess with a particular locality and the beginning of her royal patronage, in another tradition the focus is on the characteristics of her cult. The king, it is reported, adopted Markama as his family deity and chose a Brahman to be the priest in her temple. The Brahman performed the usual services for five or six days, during which the food given to the goddess was offered to the king after the puja as consecrated food (*mahaprasada*). One day, the Brahman turned his back to the goddess and received a kick in the backside from her so that he fell and lost consciousness. Meanwhile, the king, waiting in his palace for the consecrated food, learned of the priest's fall only after sending a messenger to the temple. Markama appeared to the king at night in a dream and instructed him to release the Brahman from his duty and appoint her adoptive parents as her priests. She also stipulated that Brahmans should only be used for three services, namely to perform the fire ritual (*homo*) on the seventh night of the Durga puja, and to place the sacred thread around Markama on full-moon days of the months of *sravana* (July/August) and *pausa* (December/January). Another ritual change ordered by the goddess was that henceforward the king was not to receive the consecrated food, only the water in which the goddess had been bathed.

We must now consider the nature of the relationship between tribal goddesses and Hindu little kings who were originally outsiders. Little kings of the sub-region there were probably none who had not patronized one or even several of the most important goddesses in their realms. There is evidence that neighboring little kings, or others striving for power, competed over access to the sacred site of a goddess and the status of her patron to the extent of going to war over her; occasionally, they sought to destroy the image of the tutelary goddess of their opponent, doubtless in the hope of destroying an important source of his power.

The royal patronage that was extended to tribal goddesses consisted first and foremost in the building of suitable accommodation, then in the financing of their cults and great festivals, as well as of regular puja ceremonies and in the provision for priests and their families. Mostly, the resources required for the religious services and the maintenance of professional, though non-Brahman priests, who established themselves permanently as religious virtuosi between the devotees and the goddesses, were secured

¹ . B. Schnepel, 2002. Tutelary deities: The Royal Patronage Of Tribal Goddesses in The Jungle King, pp. 245.

through small donations of land near the temples. The kings also provided funds from the treasury by raising additional payments of tribute or by raids on neighbouring kingdoms. For the goddesses themselves, the patronage of individuals with access to economic resources and political power meant an extension of their influence beyond their originally limited domains and a higher reputation. In their increased domains, they acquired the ritual recognition of most social groups, and not only, as before, of the inhabitants of one village or the members of one caste or tribe. Their temples became sites of pilgrimage, though the worship by local communities, from which the priests were also recruited, remained dominant. The local roots of these goddesses were never forgotten even though their appearance changed. They were given accommodation and a more human form. Puja was regularly performed, up to three times a day, mostly consisting of five or six *upacaras* or services, namely the offering of sandalwood paste (*gandha*), flowers (*puspa*), incense (*dhupa*), light (*dipa*), food (*bhoga*, *naivedya*) and, less frequently, a bath (*snana*).¹

It is concluded that the royal patronage of tribal goddesses can only be understood in the context of the establishment, consolidation and legitimation of political power by Hindu little kings in Hindu-tribal border regions or predominantly tribal areas. It was an important means integrating tribal and semi-tribal groups into a structure of authority based on Hindu ideas and values. In this respect, royal support for indigenous goddesses was of special importance in the early stages of a newly founded kingdom. However, in the religious history of the royal dynasties of south Odisha, there are few signs of the significance of these goddesses declining in any significant measure even in the following centuries. Only in the late nineteenth century did the cult of Jagannath begin to surpass the cult of the goddesses in popularity and political significance.

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¹ . A. Eschmann, 1978a. 'Hinduization of Tribal Deities in Orissa: The Sakta and Saiva Typology,' in: Eschmann, Kulke and Tripathi (eds.), *The Cult of Jagannath and the Regional Tradition of Orissa*, New Delhi: Manohar Publishers, Pp.79-97.